

Work-Life Balance and Work Commitment of Employees of Mining Companies in the Katangese Copper Arc

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Abstract: This study focuses on work-family life balance and work commitment in the mining companies of Haut Katanga and Lualaba in the Democratic Republic of Congo. The primary goal was to understand the challenges employees face when trying to balance their work and family responsibilities while remaining engaged at work, as well as to explore organizational policies and practices that can promote this balance.

The study reveals a diversity of individual approaches towards work-life balance, ranging from strict segmentation of professional and family spheres to positive integration of roles. Workers in mining companies face long and irregular working hours, as well as periods of prolonged separation from their families, leading to work-family conflicts. However, initiatives such as flexible schedules, parental leave and family social activities are identified as effective ways to reduce these conflicts.

The study highlights the positive impact of conciliation policies on the commitment, job satisfaction and organizational attachment of workers. Companies that offer active support for work-life balance create an environment conducive to the professional and personal development of their employees. By adopting flexible policies and practices that meet the varied needs of workers and fostering an inclusive organizational culture, companies can not only improve the well-being of their employees, but also strengthen their own long-term viability by attracting and retaining qualified talent.

Keywords: Conciliation, Professional Life, Family Life, Commitment to Work, Businesses, Mining, Flexible Hours, Organizational Attachment, KCA.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Since the opening of the Congolese mining sector to private operators in 2002, following the liberalization of the sector in accordance with law 007/2002 of July 11, 2002 establishing the mining code in the Democratic Republic of Congo, a phenomenon of intensification of the conflict between professional life and family or private constraints was observed among workers in this sector in the Katangese Copper Arc bringing together the Provinces of Haut Katanga and Lualaba. This situation mainly results from the location of mining sites in remote areas, far from urban centers where essential infrastructure is located such as schools, health centers, drinking water, electricity, and especially manpower of qualified work. Workers are thus forced to move closer to their workplace, located hundreds of kilometers from their

family home. This constant movement between the workplace and home has created an imbalance between professional and family life, accentuated by the COVID-19 pandemic which forced many workers to remain confined to their workplace.

Indeed, in some mining companies, employees are released at the end of the week after ten days of work or at the end of the month in order to return to their families for two or three days at most (Rest and Recuperation – R&R break). Others spend (apart from annual leave) around $\frac{3}{4}$ of their time at work in camps on mining sites; the ratio of family time and work time being on average 25% (Div.Travail, 2023). This observation highlights several important concerns related to work-life balance and employee work commitment.

Work-life balance refers to the balance between a person's professional and personal responsibilities (Mohamed & Dorra, 2007). This involves the ability to effectively manage the demands and responsibilities of one's professional career while taking into account one's commitments and family responsibilities (Moizard). This balance can include time management, work flexibility, and the ability to separate time spent on work from time spent on family and leisure. It is not only limited to time management, but also involves understanding the needs and expectations of workers as well as the family and cultural dynamics specific to each community (Peretti, 2016).

As for work engagement, it refers to an employee's positive and engaged state of mind towards their work and company. This manifests itself in strong personal investment, enthusiasm for professional tasks, a feeling of connection with the company's objectives, and a desire to actively contribute to its success. Work engagement is often linked to employee job satisfaction, motivation, and productivity (Peretti, 2016).

Although progress has been made in understanding work-life balance (Amstad, Meier, Fasel, Elfering, & Semmer, 2011); (Greenhaus J.H & Powell, 2006); (Gareis & Barnett, 2002); There is still much to explore to address current gaps in specific contexts such as the mining sector in the DRC. This study aims to fill these gaps by integrating cultural aspects at the local context level and the impact on work commitment (Dumas, 2008).

Our research question is: How do employees of KCA mining companies manage to reconcile their professional and family lives while maintaining a high level of work commitment?

The objective is to understand in depth how employees of KCA mining companies balance their professional and family lives while remaining committed at work.

Specifically, the study aims to explore the complex dynamics and specific challenges that workers in KCA mining companies face in terms of reconciling professional and family life, with emphasis on cultural aspects at the local level. Next, identify the policies and practices supporting work-life balance that are the most effective and impact work commitment.

The study adopts a qualitative and exploratory approach based on thematic and content analysis of semi-structured interviews carried out with employees of mining companies. Its relevance lies in understanding the needs, challenges and priorities of employees in mining companies. It provides insight into work-life balance expectations, as well as the factors that influence their engagement at work. By understanding the factors that contribute to work-life balance and work commitment, companies can implement appropriate

policies and practices. This can increase employee productivity and foster loyalty to the company.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Work-life balance is a growing concern in the modern workplace, where workers often juggle busy schedules and family responsibilities. This concern is all the more relevant in sectors where employees spend long hours at work, as is the case in the mining companies of Haut Katanga and Lualaba.

Meanwhile, work engagement, defined as the degree of dedication and enthusiasm workers have toward their work, plays a crucial role in productivity and job satisfaction (Peretti, 2016). This literature review aims to explore the different dimensions of work-family balance, with an emphasis on specific industrial contexts, and to examine how this balance influences workers' commitment within their professional environment. By analyzing previous research on this topic, this study seeks to identify the factors that promote or hinder work-life balance, as well as its impact on work commitment, thus offering valuable insights for work-life policies. Business and human resource management practices aimed at improving worker well-being and organizational performance.

The concept of “reconciling professional and family life” has entered the everyday language of political action under the leadership of European institutions and international organizations (Bihan & Martin, 2008).

Work-life balance is an individually determined and defined state of well-being that a person can or desires to achieve and which allows them to effectively manage their multiple responsibilities at work, at home and in their community, while maintaining their physical, emotional, family and community health without setbacks, stress or negative consequences. This balance has become a priority, if not the priority for organizations (Ali, Djilali, & Hamza, 2017).

Professional life can be defined as the existence led by an individual resulting from the accomplishment of a profession, an activity carried out to meet his needs (Mohamed & Dorra, 2007). Indeed, professional life means the time spent in or outside the company as part of the exercise of a job, this professional time is governed by rules defined by the employer, the margin of autonomy of the employee is relatively low and depends mainly on the mode of organization of the company and the autonomy linked to their functions (Genin, 2007). This term relates to the part of a human existence in which paid activity is carried out, any unpaid overtime and travel time to and from the workplace.

As for private life, which we understand as family life, it is everything which is strictly family, intimate, personal and which is not open to the general public (Méda & G.Dromel,

2005). We also speak of “outside work” (Kilic, 2014); we could have retained this term which refers to space-time outside of work. Some authors group under this notion all activities located in counterpoint to professional life, that is to say everything relating to personal development, family and commitment to society (Thévenet, 2004). Thus, talking about “private life” has a meaning: it is a matter of postulating that human beings, whether “active”, unemployed or retired, aspire to cultivate, in a positive way, his family, social and cultural life.

Reconciling professional activity and family is equivalent, for both a man and a woman, to assuming one's commitment and responsibilities on both fronts, without being penalized in terms of salary, career, continuing education and training. “assignment of tasks” (Michel & Pannatier, 2003). According to (Tremblay, 2005), it is a matter of making the two professional and private spheres compatible; in fact, the reconciliation between professional and private life has become a slogan. It is a concept that everyone seems to support, the term balance refers to the perception of managerial employees even if this is diverse and linked to their personal situation, but also to the representation of their role and managerial practices of the company.

Indeed, for the company, it is about creating a company culture which will allow the employee to concentrate on their work in the company. For the employee, it is a question of meeting the needs of the two spheres whose demands or necessary availabilities may be contradictory, even conflicting.

Indeed, work-life balance is defined as a type of inter-role conflict where role demands from work and family may be mutually incompatible. Also, involvement in one of the two can prevent or make investment in the other more complicated. Conflict is present when the person believes that the expectations, needs and duties of their family role are contradictory with those of their professional role, and this in a reciprocal manner (Linckens, Grodent, & Tremblay, 2011). Companies feel obliged to take into account these contextual changes, conscious of their image particularly in the context of the “war for talent”, they integrate the aspirations of younger generations for a better balance as a powerful lever of attraction (Ali, Djilali, & Hamza, 2017). There are then associated factors including the characteristics of the parents, the characteristics of the families, the characteristics of the job and the work environment which explain the type of work-family conflict. These work-family conflicts are linked either to time, to tension, or to the behavior adopted. As for the level of conflict, it concerns the degree of balance between the role of parent and the role of worker. This conflict has repercussions on physical and mental health, on marital, family and social life and on the workplace (www.stat.gouv.qc.ca, 2016).

The intensification of work-family conflict is explained by the factors of the economic context, the demographic context, the work context and the social context. These factors are at the origin of work-family conflicts over time, tension between roles and behavioral conflict. The impacts are on the family level, on work, and on the health of workers. Some research highlights the positive effects of work-life balance policies on mobilization, sense of belonging and staff retention (Chasserio, 2007).

At a practical level, guidelines are given to enable this work-family balance by maintaining parental leave, by encouraging people to reduce the period of interruption of activity and use it to prepare for a return to work, through adoption towards a child's right to be looked after by developing a specific offer, by encouraging fathers to take part of parental leave, by clarifying and, if necessary, widening the grant retirement rights for parents looking after their children, by opening paid part-time family support leave in the event of family difficulties, by strengthening the involvement of businesses and social partners and by validating acquired experience parental influence in access to employment.

For employees, work takes up a lot of time. It ensures financial security, it provides a feeling of belonging, but, above all, it is still, rightly or wrongly, the preferred means by which we value ourselves in front of others and in front of ourselves, the family is also a place where it is possible to flourish, providing the necessary care and attention to children and spouse (Wacker, 2005).

Consequently, professional commitment and time devoted to family come into competition, an active individual must then review the way they spend their energy in order to maintain personal balance and safeguard the capital of skills acquired both at their workplace than in his family place (Méda & G.Dromel, 2005); However, currently support from the employer is minimal and the working father or mother sometimes finds themselves in complex situations, making it difficult to choose between career or family life.

The interpretive framework that we have chosen is full of three main theories to explain the reconciliation of work and family life and its impact on work engagement in KCA mining companies.

A. *The Theory of Work-Family Conflict (Lewis & Cooper, 1999)*

This theory suggests that conflicts between the demands of work and those of family life can have negative consequences on work commitment. In the context of KCA mining companies, workers may face long and irregular working hours, as well as periods of prolonged separation from their families, which can lead to work-family conflicts. These conflicts can affect workers' mental and physical health, their job satisfaction, their productivity and their commitment

to the company. Workers may feel stressed, tired, unmotivated or disconnected from their company and work. As a result, their engagement and performance at work may be negatively affected.

To promote work-life balance and minimize work-family conflicts, mining companies can implement policies and practices that aim to meet workers' needs for flexibility, family support and management of the workload. For example, companies may offer flexible work schedules, parental leave, child care, health and wellness counseling, and family support programs.

By implementing these policies and practices, companies can improve workers' quality of life and job satisfaction, which in turn can increase their commitment to the company and their motivation to work effectively. Additionally, these policies and practices can help attract and retain talented workers, which can contribute to long-term business success.

B. The Theory of Work-Family Enrichment (Greenhaus & Beutell N., 1985)

This theory suggests that positive experiences in professional life can enrich family life and vice versa. In the context of KCA mining companies, workers who are satisfied with their work and feel valued may be more engaged at work and have a better quality of life outside of work. This theory posits that participation in multiple roles (such as work and family) can be a source of mutual enrichment rather than conflict. According to this theory, when work and family activities are positively interconnected, it can have beneficial effects on mental and physical health, job satisfaction and commitment.

In the context of KCA mining companies, the theory of work-family enrichment could be applied by encouraging employees to integrate their work and family lives in a positive way. For example, mining companies could encourage workers to participate in work-related social activities, such as holiday parties, sports tournaments, or family training events.

By integrating family into work life, workers could feel more engaged in their work and less conflicted by the demands of their family life. Additionally, mining companies could offer benefits such as family vacation programs or paid time off to allow workers to spend quality time with their families.

By taking a proactive approach to encouraging work-family enrichment, mining companies can help reduce work-family conflict and improve worker engagement. Workers who feel supported by their company in balancing work and family life may feel more engaged and motivated to work effectively, which can lead to benefits for the company, such as higher levels of productivity and employee retention.

C. Organizational Attachment Theory (Schoorman, Mayer, & Davis, 2007):

This theory suggests that workers who have a strong attachment to their organization are more likely to be engaged at work and feel good about their professional and personal lives. In the context of mining companies in Africa, workers who perceive their company as being committed to promoting work-life balance may have a stronger attachment to their company. Organizational attachment theory posits that individuals have an innate need to connect and remain attached to organizations to gain a sense of security, support, and identity. According to this theory, workers who feel attached to their organization tend to be more engaged, satisfied, and motivated at work.

In the context of mining companies in Africa, organizational attachment theory can help explain how reconciling work and family life can have an impact on work engagement (Charreire Petit & Durieux, 2007). If workers perceive their organization as being favorable to reconciling work and family life, this can strengthen their attachment to the organization.

For example, if a mining company offers parental leave, flexible working hours or remote working policies to enable workers to better balance their work and family lives, this can strengthen their sense of belonging to the company organization. As a result, workers can be more engaged, more motivated and more loyal to their company.

In addition, work-life balance policies can help create a positive organizational climate, which can strengthen workers' organizational attachment. Workers who perceive their organization as supportive of their well-being may be more likely to feel attached to and demonstrate commitment to the organization.

In short, organizational attachment theory can help understand how reconciling work and family life can influence worker commitment in mining companies in Africa. Mining companies that adopt policies and practices favorable to work-life balance can strengthen workers' organizational attachment, which can have positive effects on worker commitment, satisfaction and loyalty.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our research aims to study the impact of the work-family life balance of agents of mining companies in the Katangese copper arc on their commitment to work. It therefore aims to better describe and understand this little-studied phenomenon in our particular context, which places it in a descriptive-comprehensive process (Charreire Petit & Durieux, 2007).

To achieve this, we opted for a qualitative approach. Indeed, the choice of a qualitative approach can be justified as at least one of the research objectives consists either of "describing a phenomenon, or of explaining relationships, of processes, or of predicting on the basis of constructions or verification of theories, either to change social realities through experimental research or action research, or finally to master, that is to say, to propose global theoretical interpretations of the complexity of a phenomenon (Wacheux, 2005) . Our research actually meets at least one of these criteria, insofar as it aims to describe the impact of reconciling professional and family life on the organizational commitment of miners in the KCA.

A. The Research Field

KCA is a mining area located in the southeast of the Democratic Republic of Congo including the Provinces of Haut-Katanga and Lualaba. They represent 60% of the country's export revenues. In addition to being a sector that drives growth and provides formal and viable jobs in DR Congo, the choice of this sector is justified in our study also by the fact that the locations of these companies have moved away from large cities (Lubumbashi, Likasi and Kolwezi). The practices are such that agents are forced to leave their families for a certain number of days for reasons of proximity to the workplace. This is not without consequences for the work-life balance.

B. Data Collection Tools Used: In-Depth Semi-Structured Interview

The interview is one of the main methods of collecting primary data in qualitative research, along with observation. "The interview is a technique intended to collect, with a view to their analysis, discursive data reflecting in particular the conscious or unconscious mental universe of individuals. It is about getting subjects to overcome or forget their defense mechanisms that they put in place vis-à-vis the outside view of their behavior or their thinking" (Thietart, 2007). The interview is one of the unstructured methods of collecting speeches, which makes them richer than structured methods (Sem & Cornet, 2018).

C. Period, Conduct of Interviews and Choice of Sample

The interviews took place during the month of April 2022. In fact, we initially listed the mining companies which opted for the working mode with a ratio of $\frac{3}{4}$ and which in addition confined agents on the mining sites during the health crisis. We then sought to get in touch with resource people who are part of our knowledge network since it was strictly forbidden to enter or leave given the safety measures put in place. We have put together a list of contacts with an average initially of 4 to 5 people per company having practiced confinement and who, subsequently, are in the aforementioned work ratio.

D. Sample

Our necessary sample, out of the sixty people hoped for, was 38 individuals, all employees of mining companies at various levels of responsibility.

Telephone interviews took on average 30 to 45 minutes each and given the confidential nature of the data provided, these calls were made outside of normal working hours. The data collected was faithfully transcribed into word after telephone recording to obtain a corpus.

In addition to socio-demographic elements (age, gender, dependent children, marital status and number of months of confinement); The open questions revolved around the following themes:

- Questions related to reconciling professional and family life
- Questions to measure the type of engagement at work
- Questions relating work-family life balance and commitment to work.

E. Data Processing

After transcription, the data was processed with the IRAMUTEQ software which revealed three types of analyzes including lexical classification analysis, correspondence analysis and similarity analysis.

IV. RESULTS

The synthesis of the qualitative results of the study is very interesting and provides important information for mining companies in the region.

- The main proposition of the study, that work-life balance policies, family support measures and supportive corporate culture contribute to employees' work engagement, is well supported by the extracts from interviews and life experiences reported. Employees who benefit from flexible policies and family support feel more comfortable balancing work and family responsibilities, allowing them to be more engaged in their work.
- Auxiliary proposition 1, that major challenges such as restrictive work schedules and demanding conditions can impact employees' work-life balance, is also important. Unpredictable work schedules and frequent rotations can make it difficult to plan for personal life, which can lead to stress and decreased work engagement.
- Auxiliary proposition 2, according to which a better balance between professional and family life promotes greater commitment to work, is also consistent with the results of the study. Employees who have more time for their families feel less stressed at work and are more satisfied with their overall lives, making them more likely to be committed in their work.
- Auxiliary proposition 3, that family support (emotional or logistical) reduces family stress and promotes better concentration at work, is also interesting. Employees who

have support from their families feel less stressed and are more able to focus on their work.

- Auxiliary proposition 4, according to which local cultural factors (ethnicities, customs and languages) can potentially impact the way in which individuals reconcile their professional and family lives, as well as their engagement at work, is innovative and interesting. Employees who integrate cultural aspects into their professional life are more able to balance their family life and concentrate on their work.

In summary, the study shows that mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc can improve the work engagement of their employees by implementing policies and measures that promote work-life balance. This may include flexible scheduling policies, paid family leave, family support programs, and a family-friendly company culture.

A. Results of Content Analysis with Iramuteq Software

➤ Lexical Classification Analysis (LCA)

This analysis revealed four classes of words which respectively show a close relationship between professional life and family life on the one hand. this relationship also reflects the level of commitment to work which can be moderated by factors such as age, marital status, family composition, place of residence and gender.

The resulting diagram shows that employees have close relationships with their families, including parents, spouses and children. These relationships are important to employees and contribute to their overall well-being.

➤ Correspondence Factor Analysis (CFA)

The graph obtained from the text processing shows that employees with more children and family responsibilities have more difficulty reconciling their professional and personal lives. Unpredictable work schedules and frequent rotations, which are common in the mining industry, can make work-life balance even more difficult for employees with children. This analysis shows the challenges that agents in this sector face in reconciling professional and family life. The level of commitment to the work of the agents depends on this relationship.

➤ Similarity Analysis

The analysis shows that employees who are satisfied with their work-life balance are also more likely to be engaged in their work. This finding is consistent with the thematic analysis results, which showed that employees who have a better work-life balance are more likely to be happy, satisfied, and productive.

Mining companies in the Katangese Copper Arc can improve the work engagement of their employees by implementing policies and measures that promote work-life

balance. This could include flexible scheduling policies, paid family leave and family support programs.

V. DISCUSSION

The question of balance between private and professional life now occupies an important place in public debate as well as in scientific literature (Chang, McDonald, & Burton, 2010). The discussion of our results from the interviews is based on findings from the literature.

The results of the study confirm the positive impact of work-life balance policies on professional commitment. Individuals benefiting from flexible schedule policies, paid family leave or family support measures report greater satisfaction, which helps to strengthen their engagement at work. This finding is consistent with previous research (Henchoz, 2011) which highlights the importance of these policies in improving job satisfaction and employee engagement.

The positive correlation between work-life balance and work engagement is an element highlighted by the results of the study. Individuals with more time for family are less stressed at work and show higher levels of work engagement. This conclusion is consistent with the theory of work-family enrichment (Greenhaus & Beutell N., 1985), which highlights the beneficial effects of a positive interconnection between professional life and family life on satisfaction and commitment. at work.

Family support, whether emotional or logistical, appears to be a key factor in reducing family stress, thus allowing better concentration at work. This observation is supported by the literature which demonstrates that family support has a positive effect on individuals' ability to manage professional and personal challenges (Duxbury & Higgins, 2001).

Local cultural factors, such as ethnicities, customs and languages, can impact how individuals balance their work and family lives. These aspects can influence employees' priorities, behaviors and attitudes towards their work-life balance. This statement reinforces the idea that culture plays a crucial role in the dynamics of work-life balance, an aspect often supported in the anthropological literature (Matthews, Swody, & Barnes-Farrell, 2012).

Analysis of the study results through the prisms of literature and explanatory theories confirms the crucial importance of work-life balance for employees' professional engagement. Conciliation policies, family support and local cultural factors play a significant role in this dynamic. The implications of these findings suggest the need for mining companies to consider these aspects to create a favorable working environment, thereby promoting greater employee commitment and increased productivity.

Our study confirms the crucial importance of reconciling work and family life in KCA mining companies. By integrating policies and practices favorable to balance, companies can reduce work-family conflicts, promote mutual enrichment of roles, strengthen organizational attachment and respond to varied individual needs. This not only improves worker well-being and engagement, but also contributes to the long-term success of mining companies by attracting and retaining talent, thereby promoting increased productivity and

better employee retention. These findings offer valuable insights for mining companies and other industries facing similar work-life balance challenges.

Based on interviews carried out with employees and employers of KCA mining companies, we propose a model of work-life balance and work commitment-overall performance which takes into account the following relationships:

Fig 1 Explanatory Model of Work-Life Balance and Commitment to Work-Overall Performance

➤ *Managerial Impact of the Study:*

The study on work-family life balance and organizational commitment in mining companies in Africa must take into account local cultural factors to be relevant and useful. The managerial implications of such a study may be as follows:

- Understand local culture: Managers must understand local cultural norms, gender roles, family values and prevailing work practices to design suitable work-life balance policies and programs.
- Promote organizational commitment: Managers must be aware of the importance of organizational commitment for company performance. They should implement programs that encourage work-life balance, such as flexible work schedules, parental leave, and employee assistance programs.
- Educate employees: Managers must educate employees about the benefits of work-life balance and the positive impact on their well-being, organizational commitment and productivity.

- Implement appropriate policies: Managers must design work-life balance policies that meet the needs of employees based on their culture, gender, age and level of responsibility.
- Facilitate communication: Managers must facilitate communication between employees and their families, by implementing effective communication channels and family support programs.
- Encourage diversity: Managers must encourage diversity in the company, respecting cultural differences and promoting the integration of all employees, regardless of gender, age and culture.
- Measure impact: Managers should measure the impact of work-life balance policies and programs on organizational commitment, productivity, employee retention and customer satisfaction to ensure their effectiveness.

In summary, consideration of cultural factors is essential to design relevant work-life balance policies and programs in mining companies in Africa, and managers must be aware of the positive impact on organizational commitment and the performance of the company.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study on work-life balance and work commitment in mining companies in Haut Katanga and Lualaba in the Democratic Republic of Congo revealed valuable insights into the challenges, opportunities and implications for employees and businesses. In light of the results obtained and existing theories, several key conclusions can be drawn:

- Workers at CKA mining companies juggle a complexity of work and family obligations. The boundaries between work and family vary from one individual to another, and preferences for role segmentation, compensation or spillover are diverse. It is imperative to recognize this diversity to design policies and practices adapted to each individual.
- Work-life balance policies have a significant impact on worker commitment, job satisfaction and loyalty. Mining companies can foster this positive impact by offering flexible working hours, parental leave, family social activities, and emotional and instrumental support. These initiatives help create a favorable working environment, thereby improving the quality of life of workers.
- Workers' attachment to their organization is strengthened when they perceive solid conciliation policies and active support from the company. Attached workers are more engaged, satisfied and motivated. Companies can invest in creating an inclusive organizational culture that values work-life balance.
- Conciliation policies and practices should not be uniform, but rather flexible to meet the varied needs of workers. Companies should be mindful of cultural, individual and family differences when designing these policies. Individualized support can have a more significant impact on worker commitment and satisfaction.
- The study highlights the urgent need for concerted action by mining companies, local authorities and policy makers. Companies must actively integrate work-life balance into their overall human resources management strategy. Governments and international organizations can play a crucial role in developing national policies that promote a healthy balance between work and family, while respecting local cultural specificities. It highlights the critical importance of work-life balance in ACK mining companies, not only for the well-being of workers and their families, but also for long-term viability and prosperity. businesses. By investing in flexible and tailored conciliation policies and practices, mining companies can not only improve the engagement of their employees, but also contribute to the sustainable social and economic development of the region.

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